

Agroforestry in Italy

Stakeholders Policy challenges

- Bottom-up governance: the biodistrict concept for agroecology strategies and valorization of rural territories
- Agroforestry systems climate change adaptation and resilience
- Inventory of problems for each region and how was it solved
- Factsheets: current policy an AF at regional level
- Unclear, overlapped or inadequate legislation and promotion for the AF field

Policy recommendations

- 1.- Development of working groups to fit funds to existing challenges, reduce bureaucracy at minimum and adapt the legal framework for agroforestry practices implementation in both forest and agricultural land uses.
- 2.- Develop advisory systems linked to global and local research.
- 3.- Establish a short, intermediate and long term strategy to ensure agroforestry transition based on knowledge and digitalization.
- 4.- Understanding agroforestry as a land management ecosystem services provider and a value chain promotion linked to the use of the territory.
- 5.- Better understanding between the different ministries (i.e. environment and agriculture).

STATE:	Italy				
Nut level:	1				
Eurostat code:	BE2				
Area (km ²):	13.429				
Population	2018	2022			
Population	876.477	858.812			
Density (p km ⁻²)	106	103			
Cover data	2018	2022			
Forest	48,28%	62,92%			
Arable land	26,30%	9,03%			
Permanent crops	0,10%	0,82%			
Agroforestry	5,69%	8,34%			
Shrubland	2,16%	2,72%			
Grassland	10,60%	9,73%			
Agroforestry Practice Cover	2018	2022			
Silvopasture	5,40%	8,09%			
Agrisilviculture	0,00%	0,13%			
Agrosilvopasture	0,00%	0,00%			
Kitchen gardens	0,29%	0,13%			
Holding type	2016	2023			
Natural person (ha)	288.760	-			
Legal person (ha)	40.750	-			
Group holding and Common land unit (ha)	5.110	-			
Natural person (holder)	27.850	-			
Legal person (holder)	690	-			
Group holding and Common land unit (holder)	110	-			
Regional Agricultural Area	Used	2016	2023		
Farm number		28.650	-		
Farm ha (UAA)		334.620	-		

Animal populations (Thousand head)

	2018	2023
Live bovine animals	53	55
Dairy cows	7	8
Non dairy cows	5	9
Live swine, domestic species	193	202
Live sheep	178	125
Live goats	5	8

CROPS (Hectares)

	2016	2023
Utilised agricultural area	334.620	-
Cereals for the production of grain (including seed)	92.940	-
Common wheat and spelt	31.690	-
Durum wheat	24.850	-
Rye and winter cereal mixtures (maslin)	-	-
Barley	20.250	-
Oats and spring cereal mixtures	2.770	-
Grain maize and corn-cob-mix	6.790	-
Rice	-	-
Dry pulses and protein crops for the production of grain	17.310	-
Industrial crops	24.970	-
Cotton seed and fibre	-	-
Other oilseed crops n.e.c.	-	-
Fibre crops	-	-
Aromatic, medicinal and culinary plants	2.470	-

Plants harvested green from arable land	66.310	-
Green maize	1.010	-
Kitchen gardens	680	-

Rural Development Interventions promoting agroforestry

ENVCLIM(70) - Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments

Interventions	6
Forestry	6
Crop diversification including woody perennials	3
Crop rotation including woody perennials	4
Livestock including woody perennials	1
Woody perennials to reduce soil erosion	0
Woody perennials to add organic matter	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil chemical contamination	0
Animal welfare using woody perennials	0
Permanent Grasslands with woody perennials	0
Agroforestry on Permanent Crops	2
Interventions	6

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